

SIMPLIFIED ROLLING CALCULATIONS: PART 2 THE HORIZONTAL MOVING PIVOT POINT

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a pure horizontal movement of the pivot point and is the second installment in the series dealing with the rolling motion (and other motions). For the first time, this work exhibits and explains a physical phenomenon which has been observed by all and yet all researchers oblivious to it. This phenomenon occurs and is significant in small ships and boats which causes jerking and energy loss. This work shows connection between the rolling period and other parameters and jerking due to the contour of partially submerged body which is a new class of pendulum. This class of pendulum exposes a new garden of physical situations that have not been studied earlier where the pendulum path is not the typical circular arc. All the previous works of hundreds of years believed that the governing equation is based on a fixed pivot point either in the metacenter or the mass centroid, which violate the second law thermodynamics.

The oldest engineering field (marine) had several landmark breakthroughs like Archimedes (floating, and density) and Bouguer (buoyancy centroid movements) Darwin & Bessel (added mass) and this author (Pivot points, and Added Mass & Transfer properties). Previously this author showed that the governing equation is affected by the transfer properties. Thus, the righting arm is not based on the imaginary and artificial arm GM value but rather based on the real physical properties, AG . While the marine establishment has appeared to be oblivious to these developments while they really clearly fully aware of breakthroughs as discovered here (very scientific behavior!).

This analysis focus on the two dimensional abrupt and continuous case contour effects on the pivot point movement. This situation is somewhat similar to the ellipsoid pendulum which, as stated before, has not been studied. A description of

ellipsoid pendulum type (see for the description inside this article) is presented. An analytical solution for the location of the pivot point was obtained to two cases. Due to the difficulties in articulating the forces in Newtonian mechanics, the Lagrangian Mechanic had to be employed to obtained the governing equation. As opposite the common idea, the period found to be a function of the floating body contour and other parameters.

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

$\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}', \mathcal{A}''$ Pivot point at the liquid level

b Width of the body

\bar{b} The ratio of b_1/b_2

\mathcal{B} Buoyancy centroid

\mathcal{G} Mass centroid

\mathcal{K} Keel

\mathcal{M} Metacenter none existent and imaginary point

\emptyset Point on vertical after input angle

\mathcal{Z} A point on GM perpendicular to \mathcal{B}

Λ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter leftside

χ A point on the liquid line crossing the counter rightsize

Variables

a trapezoid dimension Coefficient

b trapezoid dimension Coefficient

c trapezoid dimension Coefficient

D Total Ship (body) height

\mathcal{D} New distance $\mathcal{B}'\emptyset$

d Ship draft

g Gravity constant

I Moment of inertia either body or liquid

\mathcal{L} Lagrangian
 L Angular momentum
 m Mass
 s Ship Length
 t Time
 \mathcal{T} Kinetic energy
 \mathcal{U} Potential energy
 w Ship weight
 \mathfrak{X} Horizontal distance to the original pivot point
 x Distance in straight (movement) direction
 y Distance perpendicular to x

Greek Letters

α Absolute value of difference angle right to left
 β Triangle letter as α sometimes
 ω Angular velocity
 ϕ Angle based on pivot at G (commonly undefined)
 ρ Density
 θ Input Angle
 ξ The angle $\angle AKA'$

Subscripts

0 Old location
 1 Triangle 1
 2 Triangle 2
 add, a Added mass/force
 b Floating body (ship)
 ℓ left
 r right
 xx Around the x coordinate

Key Words

Ship Rolling, Ship Frequency, Jerking Movement, Ellipsoid Pendulum, Moving Pivot Point, Changing of Moment of Inertia, Transfer Properties

1 Introduction

The ship and/or the floating body governing equation intensely depends on the moment of inertia which in turn depends on the pivot point. Commonly, it has been believed that the floating body is like a regular but giant pendulum rotating around the metacenter and later (somewhere between 195x–197x) around the mass centroid see for example (Kumar and Mitra 2023). Kumar et al’s article appeared very recently and in spite all the publications about the errors of the metacenter as a pivot point (astounding no real literature review!) and still use metacenter as pivot point. Or one of the schizophrenic belief such as (Pérez-Canosa, Orosa, Fragueta, and López-Varela 2022) which ship rotates around the mass centroid while in the same time the righting arm is based on the metacenter. Another example of pendulum with pivot point around metacenter or mass centroid (Benham, Devauchelle, and Thomson 2023). The first installment of

this series (Bar-Meir 2023f) discusses the history of the pivot point beliefs (briefly) commonly used in the ship industry and the violations the second law. Even though it has been demonstrated that both these alleged pivot points violate the second law of thermodynamics almost all the people in the field still using these erroneous pivot points. For instance, Tavakoli et al (2024) were asked why using the erroneous models like undefined moment of inertia or moment of inertia around none pivot point. Tavakoli respond that his work is based Faltinsen (2005) therefore model must be correct¹. Of course, all these models contain these nonsense which results in people doing statistical work, code name for an experimental work (to say we are clueless lets try something which really make sense), (Zhou, Li, Huang, and Liu 2023). Schizophrenic views of researchers in the area never cease to amuse and dumbfound such is (Yu, Yao, Huang, Dong, Zhang, and Feng 2023) where in the same paper the added properties according to the governing equation are constant and yet results of the calculations they become variable added properties (see figure 10 in that paper). Furthermore, there are very recent papers that simply ignore the added mass and mistakenly believe that it can be ignored (Bar-Meir 2023e). Of course, the fact that the common models are living in the fantasy realm, thus, claiming that statistical experimental work is a solution makes a lot of sense in this reality. There is a saying that in a place with only blinds, a person with a one poorly functional eye is a genius.

Maybe, this fact is the reason that no one is willing participate in a disputation on this topic with this author but only sending minions to curse this author. It must be noted that (Bar-Meir 2023f) and (Bar-Meir 2024) are very popular (probably the most read papers on the entire researchgate.net for October 2023). Thus, they cannot claim ignorance but have preference not to answer. As example of this prevalent notion presented by Weems and Belenky (2023) “[t]o a large degree, we don’t really consider that that ship ”rotates about” any point in particular” is strange. This statement captures the utterly senseless and uselessness of their analysis. How one calculated the moment of inertia of the ship or the added mass without knowing the location of the pivot point. Maybe, Weems and Belenky probably are using the special physics laws of the USA navy. Another pearl from Weems and Belenky “[t]he selection of the position about which the rotation is defined, which we call the ”node” point in the dynamics solver, is arbitrary.” According to Weems and Belenky the pivot point of the ship is arbitrary and the ship pivot point does not have to obey the physics laws. It is remarkable! One must love this genius idea, as the woke agents claims all the points on the body deserve diversity, equity, and inclusion (DE&I)! As the gem in the crown of Weems and Belenky’s response is the allegations that there is no second law violation because they did not see it and this author is a troll. One cannot see the violations, if

¹As results of this discussion a review will be written on Faltinsen’s book with G-d help.

one refuse to examine the precise statements showing the violations. Weems and Belenky's paper and papers like that are the reason that Jiang (2024) have to write a "Black-Box Modeling" code name for experimental work. One has to do this kind of experimental work because the ridiculous models which were built by Weems and Belenky and similar "geniuses" where they calculate the rotations based on moment of inertia around arbitrary pivot point (amazing, long live DEI where all the points are equal and the moment of inertia regardless to the pivot point!).

The first installment of this series (Bar-Meir 2023f) briefly discussed the history in the belief in pivot point locations of the ship industry and the violations the second law. While not specifically and explicitly, the movement of the pivot point during the rolling period was mentioned or discussed. Even in the literature review (Bar-Meir 2024) did not offer any real discussion on this point while a limit discussion appeared in this author initial stability book edition (Bar-Meir 2022e). In this second installment, the focus here on the "cooked in" change of the pivot point (it is not just a pure change of AG). The third installment will be dealing with the coupling or connection among the various "degree of freedoms" or movements. The fourth installment will be dealing with the change of the pivot point due to the heave movement (up and down) and such. The fifth installment deals with the parallel transfer theorem for the added moment of inertia. The comprehensive study of the transfer properties hopefully will appear in a different series (a very large job for one individual) hopefully soon.

Clearly, removing violations of the second law of thermodynamics and changing the governing equations that were used in the last hundred years (actually 300 years) in addition to explaining of the physics of floating bodies have been a large breakthrough job for one individual (this author). Especially, when most research works done in this area in the last several hundred years are about useless material (at best) from the physical point of view. The only useful points that comes to mind are of course the change buoyancy centroid location (Bouguer) and the added mass concept (Friedrich Wilhelm Bessel and Charles Darwin). On the other hand, the equations of motions used by all are erroneous even the thin strip theory or by other name as the slender body the idea itself while smart, but was erroneously implemented. In addition, the implementation of the added mass was not correct. While the physics "was not done with the reality in mind" (for example, no one asked where is the pivot point of roll or pitch or yaw see for example Faltinsen's book.) there are useful parts from the mathematical for instance the perturbation methods improvements and also some developments for numerical methods.

Not surprising, the idea of a fixed pivot point (even though believed to be in the wrong and different locations) is the sole concept currently exist in the marine (fish) locomotion and floating bodies (ships). It is not surprising that the idea of a fixed pivot point, even though believed to be in wrong locations, is the only one exist in the marine (fish) locomotion and floating bodies (ships). The moving pivot idea was introduced by this author (2023c). The idea of moving pivot was discussed by this author (Bar-Meir 2023c) due to the change in the added mass (due to the change orientation, change shape, etc). The current case deals with the change of pivot point for same geometry but due to the change of the equilibrium which forced a change in the pivot point. The pivot point location movements are essential for the ship maneuvering and marine creatures to control their directions/movements. These pivot point movements are due to or made by the changes of buoyancy centroid and the added mass change. These changes of the added mass are due to the change of the shape of the body like using the rudder or tail (fin) which include either changes of the shape, orientation, volume, phase change, liquid level, etc.

2 Field Elders

The literature review (Bar-Meir 2024) has shown that many, if not all, researchers are ignoring location of the pivot points without having a rational logic or any real evidence. The question why they are doing these public relationships to the erroneous work is normally answered for money (research grants or/and their reputation). The way the fields elders treat rogue free thinkers is first try to ignore them as much as possible and if this approach has fallen then they claim that all the new ideas were well known to field's elders as it stated by their minion but never can identify where it was published: The red color indicates the extracts from the minion's letters sent to this author.

[a]ll this talk about pivot point tells me you have a very limited understanding or knowledge of ship dynamics. It appears you are knocking on open doors. The topics you raise are either well-known in today's ship dynamics community, or blatantly wrong.

Note this segment was shown in (Bar-Meir 2024). The Norwegian Scientist (the minion) just can not find a reference to demonstrate anyone who discussed these ideas before or what is wrong with these ideas and why. Perhaps the following example of someone that minion is referring to. Recently, Taimuri et al (2023) stated that "[t]he origin of the body-fixed system ($o - xyz$) is located amidships on an xz -plane of symmetry and at a draft level, where the x -axis points towards the bow, the y -axis towards the starboard side, and the z -axis points downwards." While the previous papers by these authors defined/stated that the pivot point in different locations (mostly at the mass centroid). Furthermore, in a prior paper (Taimuri, Kim, Mikkola, and Hirdaris 2022) it was stated that [t]he governing equation of ship

dynamics (Fossen, 2011, Matusiak, 2021, Taimuri et al., 2020)” which is a pivot point assumed to be at the mass centroid. The Taimuri et al’s calculations seem to be actually estimated with the pivot point around the mass centroid in spite their claims. Taimuri et al approach seems to somehow attempt to reconcile with the fact that their work is basically erroneous and attempt to present their model compatible with the new idea technology (this author’s idea). It has to be pointed out the pleasant surprise as carrying the final touches to current article, people noticed the change in moment of inertia (Pan, Liu, Zhang, Liu, Feng, Ji, Zhang, and Min 2023) while almost all researchers are oblivious to the new discoveries. While the sparrows seem to arrive, there is a long way to go to remove the erroneous ideas that plague the field.

Thor Fossen and Roger Skjetne’s were/are the minion masters. The minion is from the Department of Marine Technology at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology group who would like to be called THE Norwegian Scientist while he still a graduate student he wrote to this author to express this sentiment (trying to make it look like he established scientist). This issue is brought into this paper because it represents many misunderstandings which must be illuminated and eliminated but also to point to the establishment actions because they are very important and should be presented before the public. Some of these misunderstandings might be attributed to the lack of knowledge in physics and dimensional analysis (as Skjetne is a mathematician and Fossen’s field is a cybernetics. These fields are not really related fields to dimensional analysis such as the heat transfer or even fluid mechanics. Notice that the ship stability (or navigation) is not mentioned as the proper dimensional analysis has not been really used in this field (Bar-Meir 2022a).).

Looking at another of your publications: ”In essence, the definition of the added mass of the ship means that ship is not isolated from the added mass. Hence, clearly the added mass must be part of the system”

This is an extremely inaccurate view of the ship added mass. It’s an explanation we give to first year students, and which we sometimes use in simplified models (such as the one presented in my paper). But using that representation for a paper titled ”THE GOVERNING EQUATIONS OF SURFACE VESSELS AND AQUATIC BODIES: WHY PEOPLE GET IT WRONG?” is simply ridiculous.

I am not interested in any zoom chat, and I will not let you waste any more of my time. I propose you study the work of e.g. Newman and Faltinsen. If you find any mistakes in those works, we can talk. As it stands now, you are focusing your criticism of the field on a few simplified models which, despite some inaccuracies, are sufficiently valid when used properly.

The minion approached (initiated the conversation with) this author and later he stated to say that he has no time seems to be strange. The second point is that minion brought the allegation

that he provides this material to his first year students to study this material. This statement is not possible since he did not have first year students and he did not have this material prior to the development by this author. The term “we” used by minion is either the minion has multi personalities or is talking on the behalf of his masters. The minion stated that he “determined” that (Bar-Meir 2023c) is ridiculous, yet apparently the minion and/or his masters cannot provide any explanation or logic why it is ridiculous. Neither the minion nor anyone else does have any logical physics based explanation. Such analysis is more than welcome, it is encouraged. Who knows maybe someone indeed be able to find that the second law violations are not applicable and will provide this elusive explanation. This author read what has been taught in the minion’s university and many others and none of them include this material. The minion alleged that he used this author’s idea in his paper. Now minion or anyone else should provide the papers or source where these ideas were provided. Where the minion has in his paper this material? Clearly if the minion saw it somewhere in writing. Of course, the minion is not interested in zoom or other chat app because he cannot discuss the merits of his claims or tell the truth (Initiating that discussion and yet minion does not want to loss time to continue discussion! Bluntly put, minion is lying and this is quality that no one should be proud of, especially that it can be easily verified that it is a lie like in this case.). Let say a miracle happened and this information was somehow transmitted to him telepathically, what is the logic or rational that the minion or anyone else use to dismiss this author’s ideas? Is the minion reading comprehension genuinely so poor? Or is it just a facade? It is hard to believe that one can be so dumb!

Four degree of freedoms (from the minion’s work) requires at the very least one pivot point. The special combination that the minion’s selection (not clear if he was told to write so) is one of the special case when the sway (at a constant velocity) does not affect the roll yet the roll affects the sway due to change of the added mass. As demonstration, consider an observer sitting on a ship with a constant sway velocity, the roll movement will have the same governing equation as zero sway velocity. Hence, the minion’s claim is a pure nonsense. This claim is a perfect example why almost all the works in this area that produced by these field elders violate the second law of thermodynamics and there are doubts if any other parts of their work can be salvaged. In this case, the view that the roll is created by sway movement because the minion or his masters want it, is not based on the physics laws. The term that the Norwegian Scientist use “roll center” is used mostly for cars (google it). In nautical or marine purposes it is seldom used to indicate not the pivot point but rather a point that is temporary used by roll movement (Fernandes, Asgari, and Soares 2016). In fact, it accentuates the fact of lack of understanding of the “scientists” as they claim that “a very rough estimate for the location of the roll center is halfway between the gravity centroid and the center of buoyancy.” Furthermore, ac-

According to them this center is only temporary that it is sometime work and sometime does not.

FIGURE 1. Four typical configurations of two degree of freedom of pendulum where the connections (or freedom) appear via the boundary conditions. The determination of the degree of freedom requires analysis and not always straight forward. In these cases it can be argue that it can be observed directly from the intuition.

Pires da Silva et al (Pires da Silva, Sutulo, and Guedes Soares 2023) wrote an article on “sensitivity” of the degree of freedom. The word sensitivity means or referred to the poor man (in this case should referred to the uneducated man rather than poor man) sub set of dimensional analysis (one should expect this terminology from people who are clueless about dimensional analysis thus use this terminology). One expects the examination to contain a substantive and proper literature review which this paper is missing. This article is mentioned and discussed here because it demonstrates that someone with a journal editor power and yet is totally clueless or pretending to be clueless about what is going in the field. While the arguments in the paper for a need for sensitivity analysis are reasonable, they requires to have a sound model to compare to. To compare between two failed models is not the right way to compare to reality. Citing other known faulty models like MMG family and checking the effects of the variations of the parameters is wrong way to compare to full and proper model. At the very least one expect dimensional analysis and experimental work. More details explanation are provided in the dimensional analysis chapter in (Bar-Meir 2022a).

Song et al (2024) “studied” the effect of the GM on the maneuvering of the container ship. One would expect in such paper to have an explanation how the GM is affecting the ship

movement through equation(s). At the very least, one should expect an equation with GM in paper showing the connection but the paper is listing a meaningless GM values ranging from 0.2[m] to 1.0[m] (strong indication that the authors never learn real dimensional analysis). What are these values really mean? Are they large or small? Since Song et al did not (want) to exposed their (flaws in the) model one has to get clues from other parts of the paper and other papers by these authors. The reasons that details examination of this work are presented because Song (and other authors) had a long communication with this author to explain the ridiculousness of their models. Yet, Song et al instead of providing a logical explanation or any other evidentiary evidence double down on stupidity. The teal color indicates statements of Song.

Not sure whether I understood correctly the definition of “pivot point” in your paper. But, normally, we do not regard G or M as a pivot point (where you claim the error). The actual pivot point should be somewhere between them, and we do not need it unless you confine the motion about this point. When we derive the theory regarding the metacentric height, we normally assume the the pivot point is the centre of waterline, because this is quite valid for small heel angles (by assuming submerged/emerged wedges have equal volume).

Is the DEI movement took over the marine world without this author noticing it? So many pivot points! how it is possible? How the pivot point can be in the water line (in the paper it was not mentioned) and in the same time somewhere between G and M . Is the point at water line mentioned because the Song et al read and got this idea via this author discussion this idea with them? Is the pivot point correct for small angle, why? Simply a nonsense response (probably to be safe). It must be the new DEI ideology that this author failed to recognize the new and fundamentals of basics physics class.

3 Previous Studies On This Specific Topic

This study is located on a virgin land hence a precedence review of far remote areas is suggested. The study of the floating bodies frequency suggests that examination or selection of systems that are somewhat similar so they can provide a starting point of the knowledge. In this case, the mass or/and moment of inertia of ships and similar bodies are changing during the rolling. This fact changes the governing equation. There are several situations that are candidate templates for the current and transitional situation. One kind of this family is the double pendulum or spring–pendulum type shown in fig. 1. A solution of this type normally requires two independent equations which can be, sometime, converted to a single higher order equation. This mathematical conversion, actually, indicates that there might be a strange physical behavior such as two solutions i.e. the solution is not unique or prescribe (chaos) which is not the present case.

The second family is the rolling ellipsoid type. In this case, there is really a single independent variable. The characteristic of this family is a change in the mass or moment of inertia occurs during the period of the movement yet there is only a single variable. Normally this family occurs due to the change of the pivot point or the change of the added mass or the change in added moment of inertia. The ship mass can change due to the phase change. Here, the change is due to change of contact/pivot point. In addition this mass change is associated with energy loss. This situation described by a second order differential equation which indicates that there might be a **base** frequency which depends on initial conditions or other conditions. In the previous paper (Bar-Meir 2023f) it was referred to as the base frequency which is not the observed frequency but related to it. Since this author is probably the first to step in this garden², some things might look different after some experience gained.

FIGURE 2. The ellipsoid pendulum with a single degree of freedom while the mass or the moment of inertia is changing. The moment of inertia depends on the contact point as the pivot point is at the contact point. Notice that the arm is rigidly attached to the ellipsoid.

The closest situation found in the literature is the case of the pivot point controlled or given by external force (González 2006)³. At first glance, these situations seem similar. However, Gonzalez’s scenario is different from the present case where the pivot location is controlled by the rotation angle and in Gonzalez’s case is controlled by arbitrary force acting on the body. Gonzalez’s pivot point location can change with the angle but not because the angle changes. Note that in Gonzalez’s case, the moment of inertia is invariant in almost all the cases. In addition, it can be argued that energy loss is relatively small (in addition to when neglecting the friction and such). Note that for the solid body like the ellipsoid family, the pivot point is determined by the geometry. It can be noticed that the ellipsoid in fig. 2 has four (but really only three or two and only one stable point) in the extreme possible natural equilibrium points two unstable and one very stable and one less stable (this point can be unstable). These points are determined by the attached weight and geometry.

²If you are aware of a problem related to periodic moment of ellipsoid type, not ellipsoid rolling, please let this author know about it.

³An error was found in the paper which is related to energy constraint.

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try⁴.

In current paper, the discussion is limited and the focus is on only the “horizontal” movement of the pivot point. There are also vertical movements which the current paper does not address and hopefully one of the next installment will be addressing this issue. In this discussion, it is assumed that the body is symmetrical yet some hints to unsymmetrical situations will be provided. While large ships are more in a rectangular shape a small ship (boat) has a triangular counter (cross section). This fact has a significant effect as the pivot point movement is affected by the shape of the floating body (ship). This author has not found a single reference in which really considered this effect. Thus, no literature review can be offered beside Gonzalez (2006).

In the previous paper, in this series (Bar-Meir 2023f) built model with the governing equation for the limited case of the fixed pivot point. The first and unfinished dig into the moving pivot point was done in (Bar-Meir 2021) and stopped due to adventures in the marine creature locomotion (Bar-Meir 2022b), (Bar-Meir 2022c) and, (Bar-Meir 2022d) and the die casting intensification pressure in (Bar-Meir 2023d). This work is the second attempt to finish the idea that was started earlier.

4 Prelude Definitions

The analysis of the pivot point movement due to the change in the liquid line currently does not have clear and sufficient definitions. In this series and this author’s ship stability book the rsymmetry will be defined as a shape that does not cause shifting of the physical phenomenon for example in this case the shifting of the pivot point. The rsymmetry has a general application but here only the particular case of shifting of the pivot point is presented. The rsymmetry can be examined for symmetrical bodies for example the trapezoid prisms shown in fig. 3. All these trapezoids are symmetrical (in respect to the y coordinate) but only one is rsymmetrical. The rsymmetrical shapes are more localized in nature. For example, the rectangular shape depicted in fig. 3(a) on the left is rsymmetrical because the pivot point does not change location when the body is gyrated. In that case, rounding the bottom corner or cutting them off has no effect. The exhibit in the middle (b), while symmetrical, the gyrated **clockwise** body moves the pivot point to the left, while the prisms on the right (c) when the body is gyrated **clockwise** the pivot moves to the right. The direction (left or right) is defined as if the change for the clockwise rotation. Note that for counterclockwise, the movement will be in the opposite direction. For ship stability analysis, a tilde of the body either to the left and to the right unsymmetrical and symmetrical bodies increases the moment of inertia.

⁴Even this point is a bit complicated and no general answer is known or studied (more data needed).

A point on the unsymmetrical situations, the trapezoid can be with two different angles and in the same time be unsymmetrical to the left or the right. It can be noticed that the locality characteristic of rsymmetry. The unsymmetrical bodies can be change from unsymmetrical left to unsymmetrical right. Clearly, the last change implies the body can be rsymmetrical in certain ranges.

FIGURE 3. The left exhibit shows rsymmetrical body when middle shows left unsymmetrical and right depicts right unsymmetrical body.

While the location of the pivot point for a “uniform” and symmetrical body was established in (Bar-Meir 2023a), (Bar-Meir 2023c), and (Bar-Meir 2023b) yet none of them addressed the movement of the pivot point. These concepts like the rsymmetry while seem to be straight forward yet they are not matured and it might be necessarily to revisit these concepts later on⁵. The left unsymmetrical is more common and will be discussed here. The process is centered around geometry and lead to a different physical situation since the rotation is around different pivot point hence the moment of inertia is changed during the period.

5 Abrupt Change

The step change is an extreme case where the cross section has an abrupt change at or just below within the influence range that is not much above the liquid level. As the gradual change, the abrupt change can be left or right unsymmetrical. The right unsymmetrical case is the case when the cross section is extended or expended below the liquid line and reversed is for the opposite (see fig. 4). While this situation seems simpler as compared to a gradual change, it forces an abrupt function to describe a change of the abrupt potential. There are three pivot points to each case (right or left). The first pivot point is at the center for zero inclination. For the case, left unsymmetrical (exhibit **a** in fig. 4) the pivot point moves to the left rotation is counterclock

⁵The allegations that this author received several times that he is a supper human are false and denied completely. Here is another example when this author did not make is mind or see the future. There other places that the author erred and he admits all his mistakes.

and to the right when rotation is clockwise after $\theta = 0$. In the symmetrical case, the distance $\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}$ is the same for the left movement or the right movement for the same body. In other words, the distance $\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}$ is the same negative θ or positive θ (see fig. 4).

FIGURE 4. Two abrupt bodies are exhibited. For the body on the left (a) the area is larger under the liquid level while the body on the right (b), the area under the liquid level is smaller.

6 The Lagrangian Equation

As oppose to the regular pendulum, in this case, the derivatives are not continuous and a special care has to be given to deal with the abrupt point (a discrete point at the center). For the continuous segments the governing equation is obtained from the Lagrangian equation as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\theta}} = 0 \quad (1)$$

and the Lagrangian, \mathcal{L} , is defined as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U} \quad (2)$$

Where \mathcal{T} is the kinetic energy of the system and \mathcal{U} is the potential energy of the system. It can be observed according ideal flow there is no energy lost due to pivot point because it is fixed in the segment for this reason. There is still energy loss due to the change of the shape of the floating body and the change added moment of inertia. The typical approach of control volume is actually part of the analysis as the energy in the control volume are included in the analysis. The kinetic energy, \mathcal{T} , is

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{(I_b + I_a) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} + \dots \quad (3)$$

where I_b is the body moment of inertia and I_a is the added moment of inertia both around pivot point $\mathcal{A}'_{l,r}$ (sometimes \mathcal{A}) and the \dots represents the liquid kinetic energy due to change of orientation of the body. While some progress was made on this point, the analysis is not ready for the public consumption (sorry NOT a super human). The angle θ is the angle with the origin at point \mathcal{A}' . At this stage this energy is neglected as it was done in the previous paper (Bar-Meir 2023f) and left for the next iteration. For the transition between the different pivot points the energy is not conserved but the angular momentum. Note that the angle difference angle during the transition can be calculated to be $2 \tan^{-1}((b_1 - b_2)/\mathcal{AG})$ (for the symmetrical case at the mass centroid).

6.1 Governing Equation

As oppose to the previous case, the body moment of inertia changes during the rotation not only because submerged geometry change but also because pivot location moves. This change has an abrupt point for both moment of inertia of the body and the added moment of inertia. For the symmetrical case, the body moment of inertia does not change but it is uniform with a singular point in the middle for which the moment of the inertia is reduced. Notice also the while the magnitude is the same time the direction is different. As for the unsymmetrical case, the body moment of inertia is a step function with a different value at a different step point) which occurs at equilibrium angle.

It has to be pointed out that the change of shape and change pivot are related and they can be combined or treated separably. As this work is a ground breaking, this point is not really clear and at this stage no preference can be given these options. After sometime more knowledge will be gained and a better decision(s) can be made on how to present physics.

As in (Bar-Meir 2023f) the same quantities have to expressed in terms of the problem. The potential energy can be expressed as a function of the geometry, the change in the liquid line and the change/difference of pivot point location (point and line distance). The horizontal distance pivot point move is exhibited in the left case fig. 5. The left border is at b_1 and the right border is at b_2 and middle distance (liquid line) between the two edges is $((b_1 + b_2)/2)$. Again the left hand side of border is at b_2 and subtracting this value from the middle value of the liquid line provides

$$\mathfrak{x} = \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2} \quad (4)$$

The change of buoyancy centroid for θ a tilde is done similarly to procedure outlined in (Bar-Meir 2022e). For the sake of convenience, the calculations are made when the body stay up right (and liquid line is rotated). The almost standard equation reads

$$\overline{\Delta x} = \frac{\sum \Delta x_i A_i}{A} \quad (5)$$

where

Symbol	Definition
A	total submerged area
A_i	area of element area
Δx	centroid distance in the x direction
x_i	centroid of element area

This principle also is applied to the buoyancy in y coordinate. The change in the buoyancy in the x direction is

$$B'_x = \frac{\sum B_i A_i}{A} \quad (6)$$

where

Symbol	Definition
B_i	centroid of the change element area
B'_x	total change of buoyancy in x direction
A	total submerged area ($2b_2 d$)

In this case, $B_i = \Delta x_i$. The triangle $\triangle \Lambda_0 \Lambda \mathcal{A}'$ area (see fig. 5) is added to left (movement) with centroid at $2/3$ of the length of the triangle $2(b_1 - \mathfrak{x})/3 + \mathfrak{x}$. The triangle $\triangle \mathcal{A}' \mathcal{O}' A$ is subtracted with centroid at $2/3$ of the length ($\mathfrak{x}/3$). The trapezoid $\mathcal{A} \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{X} \mathcal{X}_0$ area has to be added (it is on the right).

The trapezoid centroid is given (Bar-Meir 2023g, p. 65) The centroid in this trapezoid coordinates x value is

$$c_y = \frac{a^2 + b^2 + 2ac + bc + ab}{3(a+b)} \quad (7)$$

In this trapezoid in the coordinate x is given by

$$c_x = \frac{h(a+2b)}{3(a+b)} \quad (8)$$

The c in these equations eq. (7), eq. (8) is zero. In this case $a = (b_2 + \mathfrak{x}) \tan \theta$, $b = \mathfrak{x} \tan \theta$, and $h = b_2$ substituting into eq. (7)

FIGURE 5. The diagram to explain the notation of the land mark points for the buoyancy centroid movement.

FIGURE 6. A trapezoid to explain the notation of the centroids. Notice the coordinate system is given in the figure is adjusted to be consistent with this case thus not as it in the book.

yields

$$B'_y = \frac{\left(\overbrace{b_2^2 + 2b_2\xi + \xi^2}^{a^2} + \overbrace{\xi^2}^{b^2} + \overbrace{b_2\xi + \xi^2}^{ab} \right) \tan^3 \theta}{(b_2 + \xi) \tan \theta + \xi \tan \theta} \quad (9)$$

Or after simplifications eq. (9) becomes

$$B'_y = \frac{b_2^2 + 3b_2\xi + 3\xi^2}{(b_2 + 2\xi)} \tan \theta \quad (10)$$

Utilizing the definition of ξ eq. (4) into eq. (10) appears

$$B'_y = \frac{b_2^2 + 3b_2(b_1 - b_2) + 3(b_1 - b_2)^2}{(b_2 + 2(b_1 - b_2))} \tan \theta \quad (11)$$

Intermediate step 1

$$B'_y = \frac{b_2^2 + 3b_2b_1 - 3b_2^2 + 3(b_1^2 - 2b_1b_2 + b_2^2)}{(b_2 + 2b_1 - 2b_2)} \tan \theta \quad (12)$$

Intermediate step 2

$$B'_y = \frac{b_2^2 + \cancel{3b_2b_1} - \cancel{3b_2^2} + 3b_1^2 - \cancel{6b_2b_1} + \cancel{3b_2^2}}{(\cancel{b_2} + 2b_1 - \cancel{2b_2})} \tan \theta \quad (13)$$

These manipulations results in

$$B'_y = \left(\frac{b_2^2 + 3b_1^2 - 3b_2b_1}{2b_1 - b_2} \right) \tan \theta \quad (14)$$

or in a somewhat dimensionless form as

$$\frac{B'_y}{b_2} = \left(\frac{1 + 3\frac{b_1^2}{b_2^2} - 3\frac{b_1}{b_2}}{2\frac{b_1}{b_2} - 1} \right) \tan \theta \quad (15)$$

Denoting \bar{b} as b_1/b_2 and inserting it into eq. (15) reads

$$\frac{B'_y}{b_2} = \left(\frac{1 + 3\bar{b}^2 - 3\bar{b}}{2\bar{b} - 1} \right) \tan \theta \quad (16)$$

Observing from fig. 5 that the values of $a = (b_2 + \xi) \tan \theta$, $b = \xi \tan \theta$ and $h = b_2$ (for the trapezoid $A'O'X_0X$). With these values into substitute into eq. (8) (note the directions and the orientations are given in fig. 6) writes

$$B'_x = \frac{(b_2(b_2 + 3\xi)) \tan \theta}{3(b_2 + 2\xi) \tan \theta} = \frac{b_2(b_2 + 3\xi)}{3(b_2 + 2\xi)} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\frac{B'_x}{b_2} = \frac{b_2 + 3\mathfrak{X}}{3(b_2 + 2\mathfrak{X})} \quad (18)$$

It can be noticed that B'_x is not a function of θ . Substituting the value of \mathfrak{X} and substituting into eq. (18) results in

$$\frac{B'_x}{b_2} = \frac{b_2 + 3(b_1 - b_2)}{3(b_2 + 2(b_1 - b_2))} = \frac{3b_1 - 2b_2}{6b_1 - 3b_2} \quad (19)$$

in semi dimensionless form as

$$\frac{B'_x}{b_2} = \frac{\frac{b_1}{b_2} - \frac{2}{3}}{2\frac{b_1}{b_2} - 1} \quad (20)$$

The change in the x direction is linear without any $\tan \theta$. The ratio b_1/b_2 is denote as $\bar{b} = b_1/b_2$ which converted eq. (20) into

$$\frac{B'_x}{b_2} = \frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1} \quad (21)$$

With these values the buoyancy location can be calculated using eq. (6)

$$B'_x = \frac{1}{d} \frac{A}{2b_2} \left(\frac{\overbrace{\frac{A_i}{(b_1 - \mathfrak{X})^2 \tan \theta} \frac{B_i}{\left(\frac{2(b_1 - \mathfrak{X})}{3} + \mathfrak{X}\right)}}^{\Delta \Lambda \Lambda_0 \mathcal{A}'}}{\underbrace{\frac{\overbrace{\frac{A_i}{\mathfrak{X}^2 \tan \theta} \frac{B_i}{\left(\frac{\mathfrak{X}}{3}\right)}}^{\Delta \mathcal{A} \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{A}'}}_{\square \mathcal{A} \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{X} \mathcal{X}_0}} + \frac{\overbrace{\frac{A_i}{b_1(\mathfrak{X} + (\mathfrak{X} + b_1)) \tan \theta} \frac{B_i}{b_2 \left(\frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1}\right)}}^{\square \mathcal{A} \mathcal{O}' \mathcal{X} \mathcal{X}_0}} \right) \quad (22)$$

Utilizing eq. (4) and some manipulations eq. (22) reads

$$\frac{B'_x}{\tan \theta} = \frac{1}{2db_2} \left(\frac{1}{d2b_2} \frac{\left(b_1 - \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2}\right)^2}{2} \left(\frac{2b_2}{3} + \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2}\right) - \frac{b_1^3 - 3b_1^2 b_2 + 3b_1 b_2^2 - b_2^3}{6} + \frac{b_2 b_1}{2} (3b_1 - 2b_2) \left(\frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1}\right) \right)$$

Of further manipulation writes

$$\frac{B'_x}{\tan \theta} = \frac{1}{2d} \left((b_2)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{b_1}{4b_2} + \frac{1}{12}\right) - (b_2)^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right)^3 - 3\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right) - 1}{6} + \frac{b_2^{\frac{2}{3}} b_1}{2b_2} \left(3\frac{b_1}{b_2} - 2\right) \left(\frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1}\right) \right)$$

Utilizing the dimensionless from of b_2 reads

$$\frac{B'_x d}{b_2^2 \tan \theta} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\bar{b}}{4} + \frac{1}{12}\right) - \frac{\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right)^3 - 3\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{b_1}{b_2}\right) - 1}{6} + \frac{b_1}{2b_2} \left(3\frac{b_1}{b_2} - 2\right) \left(\frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1}\right) \right) \quad (23)$$

Utilizing the definition of $\bar{b} = b_1/b_2$ as

$$\frac{B'_x d}{b_2^2 \tan \theta} = \frac{\bar{b}}{8} + \frac{1}{24} - \frac{\bar{b}^3}{12} + \frac{\bar{b}^2}{4} - \frac{\bar{b}}{4} + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{\bar{b}}{4} (3\bar{b} - 2) \left(\frac{\bar{b} - 2/3}{2\bar{b} - 1}\right) \quad (24)$$

rearranging eq. (24) reads

$$\frac{B'_x d}{b_2^2 \tan \theta} = -\frac{\bar{b}^3}{12} + \frac{\bar{b}^2}{4} - \frac{\bar{b}}{8} + \frac{3}{24} + \left(\frac{3\bar{b}^2}{4} - \frac{\bar{b}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\bar{b}-2/3}{2\bar{b}-1}\right) \quad (25)$$

The body potential is a linear function of the distance gravity to liquid line $\mathbf{G}\mathcal{O}$. The distance between the new buoyancy centroid and the liquid line is based on the standard distance between a line and point. The distance is independent of the coordinate system and it can be arbitrary chosen. A convenient choice is when the x coordinate is set on the liquid line and origin is at \mathcal{O} and points to \mathbf{G} .

From fig. 4 it can be observed that the distance of the gravity to the liquid level is

$$\mathbf{G}\mathcal{O} = \frac{\overbrace{\mathbf{A}''\mathbf{G}}^{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}}}{\cos \theta} - \frac{\overbrace{\mathbf{A}''\mathcal{O}}^{\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A}''}}{\cos \theta} = \frac{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}}{\cos \theta} - \frac{\mathfrak{x} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}''}{\cos \theta} \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{G}\mathcal{O} = \left(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\tan \theta} \right) - \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2} \right) \frac{1}{\cos \theta} \quad (27)$$

The body potential is $U = w\mathbf{G}\mathcal{O}$ the distance between the liquid line and new position of the new buoyancy point. The coordinate system selection for these calculations is show in fig. 5. The slop is $-\tan \theta$ and y intercept is $-\mathbf{A}\mathcal{O}'$ hence the line equation is $y = -\tan \theta x - \mathbf{A}\mathcal{O}'$. The value of $\mathbf{A}\mathcal{O}'$ in terms of the problem is

$$\mathbf{A}\mathcal{O}' = \frac{\mathfrak{x}}{b_1 - b_2} \tan \theta \quad (28)$$

The line equation can be written as

$$y + \tan \theta x + \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2 \tan \theta} = 0 \quad (29)$$

The location of the buoyancy was initially at \mathbf{B} and it moves \mathbf{B}'_x to left and \mathbf{B}'_y up. Thus, the location of the new point utilizing the standard directions (up positive, and right positive) is at

$$P(x, y) = (-\mathbf{B}'_x, \mathbf{B}'_y - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}) \quad (30)$$

The distance is

$$\mathcal{D} = \sqrt{\frac{-\mathbf{B}'_x \tan \theta + (\mathbf{B}'_y - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{G}) + \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2 \tan \theta}}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \theta}}} \quad (31)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the distance between buoyancy centroid to the liquid line and it is a function θ and several other parameters.

The total potential energy of the body and liquid is

$$\mathcal{U} = \left(\overbrace{\mathbf{O}\mathbf{G}}^{\text{body}} - \overbrace{\mathcal{D}}^{\text{liquid}} \right) w \quad (32)$$

The total kinetic energy of the system is

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{(I_b + I_a) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} + \dots \quad (33)$$

where I_b is the body moment of inertia and I_a is the added moment of inertia both around pivot point $\mathbf{A}'_{l,r}$ the right or the left (and rarely sometimes \mathbf{A}). The I_a is a function of the angle while I_b for unsymmetrical is a clear step function. For rsymmetrical case it is at least a function with a singular point. Generally speaking the moment of inertia is a tensor (Bar-Meir 2022a) which is in this case the total magnitude is constant (the same r) while the tensor has different (different orientation). With a different orientation and hence has to be considered a step function. Note, in writing eq. (33) it was assumed that the liquid level remains unchanged and there is no heave motion (up and down). The last assumption is not exact as the dimensional analysis shows that there must be some heave movement but here it is neglected. However, the time frame in this case suggests that the movement is not large and in addition the movement violates a major assumption in this analysis. Thus breaking the assumption will complicate the model. Yet, this effect should be study at least experimentally but here it is assumed not to be affecting significantly.

Now with all these pieces of information, the Lagrangian can be constructed as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{(I_b + I_{add}) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} - (\mathbf{O}\mathbf{G} - \mathcal{D}) w \quad (34)$$

Equation (34) can be applied only inside the segments but not at the boundaries between the segments. As usual the procedure as

follows

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d\mathcal{L}}{d\dot{\theta}} = (I_b + I_{add}) \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{add}}{dt} \quad (35)$$

The two segments have to be sewed together when energy is not conserved even for ideal fluid (see below). For the potential energy results

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}}{d\theta} = w \left(\frac{\mathbf{AG} \cos \theta \sec^2 \theta}{\tan^2 \theta} - \sin \theta \left(\mathbf{AG} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\tan \theta} \right) - \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2} \right) - \frac{d\mathcal{D}}{d \tan \theta} \sec^2 \theta \right) \quad (36)$$

The governing equation obtains the complex form of

$$(I_b + I_{add}) \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{add}}{dt} - w \left(\frac{\mathbf{AG} \cos \theta \sec^2 \theta}{\tan^2 \theta} - \sin \theta \left(\mathbf{AG} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\tan \theta} \right) - \frac{b_1 - b_2}{2} \right) - \frac{d\mathcal{D}}{d \tan \theta} \sec^2 \theta \right) = 0 \quad (37)$$

Equation (37) is the governing equation of the rolling for abrupt counter body (minus the effects discussed earlier). While it seems that the equation has singular points ($1/\tan^2 \theta$) which suggest additional jerking points. Two points have to address here, boundary condition and the limiting case of $b_1 - b_2$. For the case $b_1 \rightarrow b_2$ the governing equation reduced to governing equation of the rsymmetrical case. This case is a limiting case which also changes the characteristic of the governing equation and boundary conditions. Note that body (pendulum) θ is not zero at boundary but has a value.

The abrupt case is an extreme case where the continuous case is somewhere between the abrupt shape and the rsymmetrical body. The change of the pivot point in the abrupt case create strange situation beside the high point at center but also strange and limited case at the new angle zero at \mathcal{A}' . At that location, the pivot switch to other \mathcal{A}' and the angle switch to the maximum angle.

The governing equation contains many terms that previously did not appear in the regular rsymmetrical case. Thus, at this stage the mathematical complication prevents this author

FIGURE 7. The mass centroid path for rsymmetrical and left unsymmetrical abrupt body. It can be observed that while in the case of rsymmetrical center minimum is at $\theta = 0$ opposite is true for left unsymmetrical case (also for the right unsymmetrical.) Note that the up and down terminology refers to the coordinate system and not to actual up and down.

to be deterministic about period beside the physical description. Especially the ratio of the expansion/contraction play important roll in the pivot point. While some ideas based on these concepts where attempts to get a patent for roll reduction, the fact remained that no one seems to have strong understanding. It can be said that these two segments have strange sewing point which currently only assumptions can be made. As the rsymmetrical can be said that metacentric does not play any role and this concept should be abandoned.

6.2 The Abrupt Transition

FIGURE 8. Schematic to explain the movement of pivot point during the transition. The body rotation pivot change dictates that the angular momentum conserved. For rsymmetrical body the change occurs at $\theta = 0$. At that angle The change from the brown pivot point to the blue results in a change of the velocities as exhibited in the from brown to blue (in the change in the y coordinate).

The connection between two segments is very interesting and deserve a discussion which might be not in the right location in this paper (so another example where this author cannot figure out everything). With these disparaging words, the actual problem can be discussed. At the point of the transition, the pivot point moves from one point to another. For example, during rotation counter clockwise at the initial the pivot point moves from \mathcal{A}'_i to \mathcal{A}'_r . At the transition the velocities of the body are complies

with a pivot point \mathcal{A}'_l and a infinitesimally small time later it must comply with the pivot point \mathcal{A}'_r thus the velocity distribution has to be adjusted instantly which forces the jerking phenomenon.

The physical quantity remains constant is the angular momentum but around the new pivot point. The coordinate system used in these derivation with origin at \mathcal{A} and the traditional direction (up, right). The location of \mathcal{A} is middle (in some cases) thus the distance $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}'_l = \mathcal{A}'_r\mathcal{A}$. The angular momentum at every infinitesimal element due to the old velocity distribution at any point on body writes

$$dL_l = r_l^2 \omega_l dm \quad (38)$$

Where dL_l is the angular momentum of infinitesimal mass around the left pivot point \mathcal{A}_l . The angular momentum with the old velocity distribution but the pivot point at \mathcal{A}'_r which creates angle $\alpha = |\theta_l - \theta_r|$ between the dm and the two pivot points. Notice that the difference velocities directions and this angle difference is identical vectors difference because both perpendicular. The net angular momentum around r_r reads

$$\mathbf{L}_{l_r} = \int_V r_l^2 \omega_l \cos \alpha dm \quad (39)$$

where \mathbf{L}_{l_r} is the angular momentum when the body rotating around the left pivot and the portion of it that creates an angular momentum around the right pivot point. The radii and α are inter depend and the integral cannot be separated or the usage of the parallel axis theorem or integration by part cannot be deployed. The angular velocity after the jump can be written as

$$\omega_r = \frac{\mathbf{L}_{l_r}}{I_r} \quad (40)$$

Clearly some of the energy is lost and the body will experience change of momentum which will cause jerking.

In this subsection the added moment of inertia was not mentioned or considered because there is no knowledge about it in this scenario. The added mass requires that a quasi steady state exist which is not the case here. The added moment most of the time has two different values at the transition from left to the right. In the simplistic the standard quasi steady state can be used. However, the actual values should be larger under the argument that more liquid must be displaced. The dimensional analysis of this argument is not mature enough and thus not present here.

7 Continuous Unsymmetrical Case

This case deals with a continuous changing area, symmetrical and unsymmetrical case. As it was done in the previous problem of the abrupt shape, the Lagrangian with its elements has been calculated. As oppose to the abrupt case the pivot point has to be calculated. After this calculation, the change in the buoyancy has to be found. This physical situation requires large amount trigonometric manipulation very laborious but straight forward. As this paper is a draft for the chapter in the book(s) some of the details will be abstract and will be provided when requested if possible.

The symmetrical triangle provides a frame work for different shapes as all the shape can be considered to be as triangle for small enough angle. The more general case is when the body with unsymmetrical either left or right in addition with unsymmetrical counter. This situation will be only briefly discussed here.

In these calculations the following auxiliary equation will be used which the area expressed as a function of one side triangle plus two side angles as

$$A = \frac{c^2 \sin^2 \alpha}{2 \sin(\alpha + \beta)} \quad (41)$$

The body shown in fig. 10 is left unsymmetrical and hence the

FIGURE 9. The notation of the triangle for the area calculations. Note that α and β are double dip as it has two definition based on the context.

buoyancy point will move to the left. The original buoyancy centroid was at the center at the submerged part (at $0, 2d/3$) when the coordinate system origin is at \mathcal{A} and x point to right and y point up. While the contour of the ship or floating body can appear in many shapes, the first approximation that come to mind is a triangle prism. The symmetrical triangle provides a frame work for different contours as all the contours can be considered to be triangle for small enough angle. The more general case is when of two angles (sides) of the triangle are unequal is not solved but only briefly discussed. For the standard triangle, the following relationship can be written as it based on law of sines.

The trick in these calculations is to find the right variable which minimizes the calculations' labor and in this case, it seems to be ξ (or \mathfrak{X}) or in other words the angle $\angle \mathcal{A}\mathcal{K}\mathcal{A}'$ (see fig. 10).

The areas (in the dark cyan) 1 and 2 have to be identical as it is a fundamental requirement that the ship displacement remains constant.

$$A_1 = A_2 \quad (42)$$

The triangle 1 area is computed by $c = \mathcal{A}'\Lambda_0 = d(\tan\beta - \tan\xi)$, " $\alpha'' = \theta$ and " $\beta'' = \pi/2 + \beta$ from eq. (41) the area becomes

$$A_1 = \frac{d^2(\tan\beta - \tan\xi)^2}{2} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\sin(\pi/2 + \beta + \theta)} \quad (43)$$

The triangle 2 area is computed by $c = \mathcal{A}'\chi_0 = d(\tan\beta + \tan\xi)$, " $\alpha'' = \theta$ and " $\beta'' = \pi/2 - \beta$ ($\angle\mathcal{K}\chi_0\mathcal{A}'$) from eq. (41) the area becomes

$$A_2 = \frac{d^2(\tan\beta + \tan\xi)^2}{2} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\sin(\pi/2 - \beta + \theta)} \quad (44)$$

Substituting eq. (43) and eq. (44) into eq. (42) reads

$$\frac{d^2(\tan\beta - \tan\xi)^2}{2} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\sin(\pi/2 + \beta + \theta)} = \frac{d^2(\tan\beta + \tan\xi)^2}{2} \frac{\sin^2\theta}{\sin(\pi/2 - \beta + \theta)} \quad (45)$$

with the identity of $\sin(\pi/2 + \beta + \theta) = \cos(\beta + \theta)$ and $\sin(\pi/2 - \beta + \theta) = \cos(\beta - \theta)$ eq. (45) becomes can written as

$$\left(\frac{\tan\beta - \tan\xi}{\tan\beta + \tan\xi} \right)^2 = \frac{\cos(\beta + \theta)}{\cos(\beta - \theta)} \quad (46)$$

which can be written as

$$\xi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{\frac{\cos(\beta + \theta)}{\cos(\beta - \theta)}}}{1 + \sqrt{\frac{\cos(\beta + \theta)}{\cos(\beta - \theta)}}} \right) \quad (47)$$

Equation (47) is the equation for the angle ξ . The pivot point distance from the old \mathcal{A} which is a function of β , θ and d . The angle described in eq. (47) (for ξ) must be in the first quadrant and all other solutions should be rejected. This author did

not find supper clean analytical solution to eq. (46) but this form seems sufficiently clean.

At this stage the change in the buoyancy centroid is carried out where ξ is considered solved and thus also \mathfrak{X} .

FIGURE 10. Isosceles triangle prism with input angle of θ and with angle of β

As the oppose the previous case here the new buoyancy location can be calculated using the vertices. The mass centroid of the triangle $\Delta\mathcal{K}\chi\Lambda$ can be obtained from the information on the location of the vertices. For coordinate system with y up positive and x to the right is positive and origin at \mathcal{A} , the location of \mathcal{K} is at $(0, -d)$. The distance of $\mathcal{A}'\chi$ according to sines law (the $\Delta\mathcal{K}\mathcal{A}'\chi_0$) is

$$\mathcal{A}'\chi = \frac{\frac{\mathfrak{X} + b/2}{d(\tan\xi + \tan\beta)} \frac{\sin(\pi/2 - \beta)}{\cos\beta}}{\frac{\cos(\theta - \beta)}{\sin(\pi/2 - \theta + \beta)}} \quad (48)$$

The height z (inside the area 2) reads

$$z = \mathcal{A}\chi \sin\theta = \frac{d(\tan\xi + \tan\beta) \cos\beta \sin\theta}{\cos(\theta - \beta)} \quad (49)$$

distance is

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{B_x - \tan \theta B_y - \mathcal{A}\mathcal{O}'}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \theta}} \quad (61)$$

With all the elements defined the governing equation can be expressed.

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{(I_b + I_{add}) \dot{\theta}^2}{2} - (\mathcal{O}\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{D}) w \quad (62)$$

Now as oppose the abrupt case, the body moment of inertia for the entire path varies. The total kinetic energy of the system is

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d\mathcal{L}}{d\dot{\theta}} = (I_b + I_{add}) \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{add}}{dt} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{body}}{dt} \quad (63)$$

Oppose to the abrupt case where the body moment of inertia was continuous for segments, here the body moment of inertia is variable. The parallel axis theorem exist for any solid body like a floating body (ship) and reads

$$I_{body} = I_o + m\Delta r^2 \quad (64)$$

where I_o is moment of inertia around mass centroid which is constant. However, the r in this case $\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}$ is function of θ which turn out to be a function of the time. Hence, derivative in eq. (63)

$$\frac{dI_{body}}{dt} = \frac{d(I_o + m\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}^2)}{dt} = 2m\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G} \frac{d\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}}{dt} \quad (65)$$

where m is the mass of the floating body (ship). The distance $\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}$ can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G} = \sqrt{\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{O}^2 + \mathcal{G}\mathcal{O}^2} \quad (66)$$

where $\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{O} = \mathcal{X} + \mathcal{A}\mathcal{G}\tan \theta$ and $\mathcal{G}\mathcal{O}$ given by equation eq. (58). The expression for derivation are straight forward but very long which complicated the visualization.

$$\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{G}^2 = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{G}^2 (\tan \theta + \tan \xi)^2 \cos^2 \theta + (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{X} \tan \theta)^2 \cos^2 \theta \quad (67)$$

The derive for the Lagrangian of the function (θ) is

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}}{d\theta} = w \frac{d(\mathcal{O}\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{D})}{d\theta} \quad (68)$$

The period is affected by function or by the function in power like θ^2 and higher. In case, the governing equation is complex made by different trigonometrical functions which there is not significant theoretical knowledge. At the present junction, the numerical solution is the answer.

The governing equation is

$$(I_b + I_{add}) \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{add}}{dt} + \frac{d\theta}{dt} \frac{dI_{body}}{dt} - w \frac{d(\mathcal{O}\mathcal{G} - \mathcal{D})}{dt} = 0 \quad (69)$$

when all was defined previously. Note the energy was assumed to be conserved that is reasonable only very mild counter. If larger slop appear then there the energy loss must be considered.

8 Concluding Remarks

The current paper examines the effect of counter on the governing equation and possibly natural frequency. In the complexity of the governing equation it seems the character of the question has to be study first. The location of the pivot point was explicitly defined and calculated in this analysis. That seems from the discussion is that the moment of inertia change also affects the added moment of inertia. This fact means that relatively larger energy is loss and it can be used to reduce rolling energy and hence increase the safety of the ship.

Obviously this papers series is different from all the papers published in this area in the past. The effects of the contour show possible way to increase the stability of the ship. This author is not a shame to exposed that the establishment belief is full with misconceptions and the field elders will go after this author by sending minions or ignore him as much they like. The new line of accusation attack against this author by sending minions by claim that this author use his supper abilities to bully and humiliate scientists is strange. This line of attack will irritating will be ignored in the future. Thus, if you believe that the ideas and analysis in this paper are correct, you should change the way you deal with the ship/fish/aquatic propulsion. If you do not believe in these ideas, you are welcome to criticize this author's current or future papers (all or any of papers in this area), in any form, all remarks in writing or electronic are appreciated (please do not call this author who do not like to deal with too emotional people.). There are several web cites and forums dedicated to criticize and discuss this author's work for you can choose from

those.

This paper is the second part of the installment in this series. Currently, the third and fourth parts are in a draft form and may or may not be published and might join the faith of many unpublished papers of this author, laying in his boxes. A small point, in writing these papers a new technology was used. The equations derivations were typed straight into enclosed confidential and supper confidential environments (for this author eyes only) which do not appear in the final version. Hence, if something is rasping, it is due to this dual writing style.

Disputation

After the minion from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and probably his masters (it hard to believe graduate student done it by himself) issuing the claims that either all was known or if it was not known it must be wrong, here is a challenge for minion and his masters. Additionally there are those quietly belief in these claims without advertise their belief. Furthermore, there are those who put the horse blindfold to minimize their exposure the new technology like Carolyn Q. Judge so they will not realize their work was useless/wrong. With about five billion dollars in research grants and producing research papers that violate the second law of thermodynamics it is time to examine these claims. This author is calling for disputation since the subject is science and true matter. If you believe in one or more of the topics below you have an invitation for disputation.

These topics are

1. The pivot point of the rolling or pitching is either in the metacenter or mass centroid or “rolling center” or “somewhere between the metacenter and gravity centroid”. The rolling center mentioned in this paper.
2. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
3. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant. As the governing equations as defined in Fossen or MIT or Caroline Judge classes.
4. The pivot point is constant in the ship navigation equations.
5. If you believe that MMG equations are correct or logical or sensible.
6. If you believe the strip theory as is described or is correct as in MIT’s classes .
7. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass (a core belief in the common establishment doctrine).
8. If you believe that more 50% of the world research in the ship stability/navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics.

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This paper that describe a progress in this magnitude has some willing and unwilling partners. First, thank you for Naomi Mar-

shak who corrected the English of early draft of the first 6 pages which her questions added more material. Second, the unwilling participants such as Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to “protect” her students from the truth. Several other individuals from Gdańsk University that through the discussions with them demonstrates how the fads persuasive around the world. As example of fad’s believer Dr. Song provided inspiration on how one can double down on stupidity is so amusing. Some discussion elements on parallel theorem remained and persist in this paper please ignore those. Also Kostas Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deals with the “rogue agent” by netscaping his/their material.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Bar–Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He has differentiated between the added properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for centroid of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar–Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar–Meir’s book. Dr. Spyrou’s behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar–Meir’s calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford

University recently decided to copy Bar-Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes) to this idea. Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar-Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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